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1st INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON SUSTAINABLE COMMUNICATION, MACHINE INTELLIGENCE, AND METAVERSE (SCMIM - 2025)

7th – 8th FEB
2025 (IST)

(Hybrid Mode)

CALL FOR PAPERS FOR

**Nature Knowledge Computing Unknown
Diversity Learning to Known Wireless
Network 2024**

Special Session: 21

Follow the link or scan below QR to
submit your paper to the special session

SESSION ORGANIZER(S)

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RECOMMENDED TOPICS

Nature Knowledge Computing
Diversity Learning Moment-based Diversity Network
Dynamic Topology System using Gen AI
Network Optimization
Security System for Personalized Device

Publications:

- Selected papers of the conference will be published in **Springer Proceedings in Information and Communication Technologies** [<https://www.springer.com/series/17395>]
- Opportunity to publish as book chapter in highly reputed international publishers like Scrivener-Wiley, Apple Academic Press, ISTE-Wiley etc.
- Selected extended papers will be recommended to **Scopus / SCIE-indexed** journals, associated with SCMIM-2025.

*Published edited books/proceedings will be submitted for indexing in major academic databases like Scopus etc by respective publishers.

SUBMISSION PROCEDURE

- ✓ Mention the **appropriate Special Session No. & Title** at the top of your manuscript.
- ✓ Login to CMT (follow the link/QR), at the Author Console (SCMIM2025) - **+Create New Submission**, you have to **choose the appropriate Special Session No. & Title** from the drop down list under the **"Paper Submission"**.
- ✓ For templates and guidelines follow conference website:
<https://mckvieconferences.in/full-paper-submission-and-author-guidelines/>

Paper Submission Link:

<https://cmt3.research.microsoft.com/SCMIM2025>

Paper Submission Deadline: 15th OCT 2024

Acceptance Notification: 30th DEC 2024

Registration Deadline: 5th JAN 2025

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